

INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIPS AMONG THE THREE DIMENSIONS OF CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The concepts of corporate sustainability performance (CSP) calls for a convergence between the three overlapping aspects: economic development, social equity, and environmental protection. Integration of sustainable business practices (SBPs) (i.e. economic, environmental and social) in businesses has gained extensive attention in recent times owing to the escalating pressures from different stakeholder groups. To investigate this phenomenon, this study developed a conceptual framework to explore the impact of environmental and social performance on a firm's economic bottom line, based on a large-scale questionnaire survey in the Bangladeshi RMG industry. A total of 255 responses were analyzed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to identify the relationships among the different performance dimensions of CSP. This study confirmed that there is a positive impact of both environmental and social performance on economic performance. It is worth noting that environmental performance has a more significant positive effect on a firm's financial performance than social performance. The results of this study offer valuable insights into the managerial decision-making process by informing corporate managers, as well as policymakers, the interlink among all three dimensions and how the improved environmental and social performances positively influence a firm's economic performance.

Keywords : *Economic, Environmental, Performance, Readymade Garments, Sustainability, Social.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Elkington (1994) defines sustainability in terms of Triple Bottom Line (TBL), also known as “people, planet, profit”, a formulation that helps organizations to expand their focus from a single bottom line of financial performance to include social and environmental performance (Isaksson et al., 2015). CSP measures the extent to which a firm incorporates economic, environmental, and social business practices into its operations, hence impacting these practices on business and society (Artiach et al., 2010). According to the TBL approach proposed by Elkington in 1994, there are three dimensions of CSP: economic, environmental and social. Figure 1 shows the three dimensions of CSP.

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Figure 1 : Dimensions of Corporate Sustainability Performance (CSP)

The economic performance, also known as the financial performance, of the firm is measured in terms of its profit margin, sales volume, Return on Investment (ROI), Return on Assets (ROA) and market share. Environmental performances are measured using an amount of waste reduction, adoption of resource efficiency practices (e.g., reuse, recycle), reduction in consumption of hazardous materials, pollution prevention, and adoption of environmental management systems (EMS). Ensuring the health and safety of employees, community development practices, ensuring employee well-being, and adopting social certifications are generally used to evaluate an organization's social performances. Since the underlying dimensions of the CSP is a multi-dimensional concept which itself has often shown conflicting relationships among the dimensions (Bebbington, 1997).

The RMG sector is considered one of the main contributors of unsustainable business practice in Bangladesh due to its high carbon emission, extensive usage of chemicals and natural resources. Frequent instances of environmental degradation and human rights violations in the RMG industry have caused corporate sustainability to become an issue for discussion amongst several stakeholder groups. Hence, it is the RMG sector's responsibility to find innovative solutions in achieving enhanced corporate sustainability performance (CSP). A limited number of previous studies addressed all three dimensions of CSP and the impact of one dimension on others in developing country's context in general and RMG industry's context in particular (Qu et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2018; Afzal et al., 2017; Ye et al., 2015; Cantele & Zardini 2018; Rashid et al., 2016; Wijethilake, 2017). This study investigates this phenomenon in the Bangladeshi RMG industry's context, and hence the objective of this study is to:

- Explore the relationship among the three dimensions of corporate sustainability performances.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

There exist several studies in the literature related to corporate sustainability performance (e.g., Gimenez & Tachizawa, 2012; Sarkis et al., 2011). Seuring and Müller (2008) reviewed 191 papers published from 1994 to 2007 and classified the corporate sustainability performance literature into six categories: sustainable, environmental, ecological, green, social, and ethical. Traditionally research has focused primarily on measuring sustainability performance in terms of the economic

dimension of the TBL, such as competitiveness, and in particular, cost, quality, speed, flexibility and reliability of performance objectives (Gunasekaran & Kobu, 2007; Akyuz & Erkan, 2010; Taticchi et al., 2013). However, the environmental performance has gradually attracted academic researchers' attention (Holt & Ghobadian, 2009; Testa & Iraldo, 2010). However, very few publications focus exclusively on social performance measures reflected in terms of improved health and safety issues, social benefits and increased employment opportunities (Perry & Towers, 2013; Das, 2018). Recently, a limited number of studies have started to contribute explicitly to the essentially holistic view of sustainability (Hassini et al., 2012; Qu et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2018; Afzal et al., 2017; Ye et al., 2015; Cantele & Zardini, 2018; Wijethilake, 2017; Alsayegh et al., 2020).

In the mid-90s, Porter and Van der Linde (1995) predicted that the implementation of an Environmental Management System (EMS) would improve an enterprise's competitive advantage and improve its market share by promoting a positive company image. For this reason, the area of EMS has attracted substantial attention from both academics and practitioners (Ambec & Lanoie, 2008; Amores-Salvadó et al., 2015; Wagner, 2015). Multiple studies have empirically revealed that EMS can enhance a firm's reputation, brand and trust to attract customers and employees and ultimately increase profitability (Porter & Kramer, 2011; Song et al., 2017). In their study, the authors found a statistically significant relationship between EMS and organizational financial performance regarding the return on assets (ROA) (Waddock & Graves, 1997). On the same note, according to Klassen and McLaughlin (1996), environmental disclosure and management improve a company's financial performance by either increasing operating income or reducing product expenditure. Several empirical studies established a positive relationship between environmental practices and company performance (Yu et al., 2017; Henri & Journeault, 2010; Wagner, 2015; Chan et al., 2016; Eiadat et al., 2008; Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017; Severo et al., 2017; Amores-Salvadó et al., 2015; Feng et al., 2016; Nishitani et al., 2017). In their study, Yu et al. (2017) established that an environmental innovation strategy fully mediates the relationship between stakeholder pressures and environmental performance and partially mediates the effect of environmental regulation on financial performance in UK firms. Similar studies in this research area found that the stronger the environmental innovation strategy, the better the firms' business performance (Eiadat et al., 2008; Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017). In their latest study, Xie and Zhu (2020) argued that green training positively impacts corporate sustainability performance through the indirect effect of green innovation behaviour. In their study, Qu et al. (2015) argued that managers' environmental awareness helps drive and transform environmental practices into sustainable development performance in Chinese eco-industrial parks. A recent study showed that environmental performance improves economic performance by improving the production process directly through the sustainable consumption and production (SCP) process (Nishitani & Kokubu, 2020). Numerous studies in the current literature recommend companies to combine cleaner

production and environmental management with improving financial gain, return on assets and market performance (Severo et al., 2017; Amores-Salvadó et al., 2015; Lo et al., 2012).

However, several recent studies also reveal negative impacts within these relationships (Lucato et al., 2017; Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017; Thornton et al., 2003). Lucato et al. (2017) argue that their research is in line with those authors who failed to establish a positive correlation between companies' environmental and financial performances. Hojnik and Ruzzier (2017) also argued that their study revealed a statistically non-significant relationship between ISO 14001 and firm performance. Thornton et al. (2003) show inconsistent relationships between environmental performance and profitability; Wagner et al. (2002) suggest that the relationship between environmental and economic performance is uniformly negative. Voinea et al. (2020) argued that the negative impact of environmental performance on financial performance might indicate that the assets required to apprehend an enhanced environmental performance correspond to high environmental management maintenance and overhead costs.

On the other hand, socially responsible practices, if strategically managed, can also add value and competitiveness to the company (Neubaum & Zahra, 2006; Porter & Kramer, 2002) and foster its financial performance (Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Freeman 1984; Feng et al., 2016; Lo et al., 2012). The study's findings conducted by Rodriguez-Fernandez (2016) demonstrate positive relationships between social business practices and profitability. Rodriguez-Fernandez (2016) carried out an empirical study on the companies registered on the Madrid Stock Exchange and concluded that there exists a positive relationship between social and financial performance. The improved health and safety conditions positively impact employees' motivation and morale, leading to increased productivity and reduced costs of new recruitment (Brammer & Millington, 2008; Alsayegh et al., 2020). In their research, Nollet et al. (2016) proposed a linear model, and results suggest a significant negative relationship between social performance and Return on Capital. These authors argue that this negative relationship resulted from the cost of long-term planning and the considerable sum of resources dedicated to improving social performance.

A limited number of previous studies address all three dimensions of CSP (Qu et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2018; Afzal et al., 2017; Ye et al., 2015; Cantele & Zardini, 2018; Rashid et al., 2016; Wijethilake, 2017). The results of an empirical study performed by Cegarra-Navarro et al. (2016) found that the social, environmental and economic dimensions of sustainability positively affect the firm's competitive advantage, mediated by corporate reputation, customer satisfaction and organizational commitment. The conclusions of a similar study conducted in Australia illustrate that social performance consistently leads to improved economic performance and that environmental performance also had a positive effect on financial performance (Sila & Cek, 2017). Rashid et al. (2016) established in their study that the sustainable manufacturing process and end-of-life management approaches have a significant positive influence on all three dimensions of CSP. Similarly, Wijethilake (2017)

revealed that implementing an integrated system such as the ‘Sustainability Control System’ had a partial mediating effect on the relationship between proactive sustainability strategy and corporate sustainability performance.

In contrast, the results of another study argued that although companies are using sustainable innovation strategies to support all three dimensions of CSP, in reality, they are more concerned about economic achievement, i.e., improved financial performance (Cegarra-Navarro et al., 2016). The results of this review of previous literature indicate that financial performance is still the primary target of most organizations (Afzal et al., 2017; Alsayegh et al., 2020). Although companies are using innovative strategies and systems to support economic, environmental and social achievements, in reality, they are only aiming to improve financial outcomes to maximize their market value on a long-term basis (Cegarra-Navarro et al., 2016; Alsayegh et al., 2020).

The existing literature produces mixed results regarding the relationship between all three dimensions of corporate sustainability performance. Some researchers argue that superior environmental performance can lead to a better financial performance by improving firms’ market share, brand image and profit margins (Klassen & McLaughlin, 1996; Jacobs et al., 2010; Amores-Salvadó et al., 2015). According to Heal (2005), superior environmental performance (i.e., better resource management, cleaner production, waste reduction, recycling, reuse of materials, reduction in consumption of hazardous materials, and adoption of ISO 14001) provides benefits, including improved financial performance through greater operational efficiency, enhanced reputation and competitiveness. Multiple studies have demonstrated empirically that those environmental practices can also enhance a firm’s profitability (Porter & Kramer, 2011; Song et al., 2017; Waddock & Graves, 1997; Klassen & McLaughlin, 1996). In their latest study, Alsayegh et al. (2020) claimed a significantly positive relation of environmental performance and social performance with economic sustainable performance. A recent study conducted by Le (2020) revealed that green design and manufacturing had a significant positive effect on all three dimensions of CSP. Furthermore, a firm’s green image can reduce business risk by decreasing the threat of penalties and litigation associated with not complying with environmental rules and regulations (Song et al., 2017). The study conducted by Khan et al. (2020) shows that the usage of renewable energy in logistics operations will improve environmental and economic performance through reduced emissions.

Several empirical studies established a positive relationship between environmental performance and economic performance (Yu et al., 2017; Henri & Journeault, 2010; Wagner, 2015; Chan et al., 2016; Eiadat et al., 2008; Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017; Severo et al., 2017; Feng et al., 2016; Nishitani et al., 2017). Numerous studies in the current literature recommend that companies combine resource-efficiency practices and ISO 14001 to improve financial performance (Severo et al., 2017; Amores-Salvadó et al., 2015; Lo et al., 2012). However, several studies also revealed negative impacts of environmental performance on economic performance resulting from massive investment in the implementation of the environmental practices and training, as

well as infrastructure development and technology advancement (Lucato et al., 2017; Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017; Thornton et al., 2003; Wagner et al., 2002).

Implementation of socially responsible practices can help a firm in its profit maximization (Neubaum & Zahra, 2006; Porter & Kramer, 2002) and enhance its economic performance (Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Freeman, 1984; Feng et al., 2016; Lo et al., 2012; Rodriguez-Fernandez, 2016). Instead, several studies have also recorded contradictory results by revealing a significant negative relationship between social performance and financial outcomes (Nollet et al., 2016; Sila & Cek, 2017). Sila and Cek (2017) claim that social performance consistently improves economic performance compared to environmental performance. This study explores this phenomenon in a developing country’s context by investigating the impact of environmental and social performance on economic performance, as shown in Figure 2. Hence it was hypothesized that:

H1_a : There exists a positive impact of improved environmental performance on economic performance.

H1_b : There exists a positive impact of improved social performance on economic performance.

Figure 2 : Conceptual Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

The primary data collection method for this study was the large-scale questionnaire survey. Firstly, a draft questionnaire was prepared based on the following theoretical constructs: corporate sustainability performances (economic, environmental and social). The items of these theoretical constructs were developed based on an extensive literature review. Table A1 in Appendix 1 outlines the constructs operationalized for this study. The draft questionnaire was pilot tested to ensure the validity of the instrument. Subsequently, the questionnaire was distributed to the chosen sample from a target population using snowball sampling. For this study, all precaution were taken into account in designing and constructing the questionnaire to develop a clear, unambiguous and useful document. Both online and self-administered survey methods were employed to carry out a large-scale survey. The last part of the questionnaire contains demographic information (i.e., company’s annual turnover, size).

All items except the demographic information were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 “Strongly Disagree” to 5 “Strongly Agree” for the survey questions. Likert scale is a very widely accepted scale level of agreement or disagreement designed to measure attitudes or opinions (Bowling et al., 1997). Data collected using the Likert scale are easily quantifiable and are suitable for the computation of various sophisticated statistical analyses.

3.1 Research Population and Sampling

This research project investigates the relationships among the dimensions of CSP on the RMG industry of Bangladesh to improve corporate sustainability performance. The population of interest to this study were the listed RMG companies in the **Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA)**, which is one of the largest trade associations in Bangladesh, representing the readymade garment industry. BGMEA presently has around 4,500 member companies who are mainly the suppliers of readymade garments to the international market (BGMEA, 2019). To the best of the researcher’s knowledge, the concept of sustainability is still considered an emerging phenomenon in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. For this reason, it is not rational to use the random sampling technique to choose the respondents. In this situation, a snowball sampling technique (also known as chain-referral sampling) was considered appropriate by the researcher to examine the proposed framework of RMG companies.

The target respondents of this study were the top and mid-level corporate managers, compliance managers or sustainability managers chosen from the large and medium-sized Bangladeshi RMG industry. Initially, the researcher nominated a group of respondents from reputable large RMG companies based on some set predefined criteria as listed below:

- (a) Publication of standalone sustainability or UNGC reports
- (b) Achievement of international and national level sustainability-related award
- (c) Adoption of sustainable business practices (e.g., construction of LEED-certified green factories)
- (d) Achievement of social and environmental certifications such as SA 8000 and ISO 14001
- (e) Presence of a formal sustainability committee or dedicated sustainability managers

This study used exponential ‘snowball sampling’ where the nominated respondents will provide multiple referrals first. Then each new referral will suggest another set of new referrals, and this process continues until primary data from a sufficient amount of samples have been collected (Dudovskiy, 2016).

3.1.1 Sample Size

The reliability and validity of this statistical analysis vary hugely with the differences in sample size. The statistical procedures involved in this study include exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modelling (SEM). There are several well-known rules of thumb in the literature for selecting the sample size of factor analysis. Gorsuch (1990) and Kline (2014) suggest that the minimum sample size should be at least 100 subjects. Comrey and Lee (1992) recommend the scale of sample size adequacy: 50 – very poor, 100 – poor, 200 – fair, 300 – good, 500 – very good, and 1,000 or more – excellent. Both Everitt (1975) and Nunnally (1978) recommend sampling at least ten times as many subjects as variables. A total of 650 questionnaires were distributed to the RMG companies who were listed in BGMEA, using snowball sampling. A total of 255 responses to 650 questionnaires were received, which corresponds to an overall response rate of 39.23%.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is imperative to conduct the initial data screening to generate a clean and accurate data set for further statistical analysis in any multivariate analysis. This study critically examines the data collected before running the sophisticated multivariate statistical analysis, such as Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). After completing data collection, in the next step, this study conducted the data screening, which includes an assessment of missing data, outliers, multicollinearity and normality. In this study, IBM SPSS 23.0 is used to perform the data screening and to delete or modify required data entry to avoid undesirable outcomes. Missing data, miscoded data and outliers were determined by using descriptive statistics that were calculated using SPSS.

Generally, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is utilized to discover the factor structure of a measure to generate a theory or model from a comparatively large set of latent constructs (Williams, 2010). This study applies Principal Axis Factoring (PAF) because the researcher had a piece of prior knowledge about the underlying structure of the latent constructs. The study uses the SPSS and AMOS programs to analyze the data. All the items of each scale had high factor loadings between 0.500 and 0.900, meeting the desirable value of 0.50 as recommended by Hair et al. (2006). Two measurement items ECOP1 and SCOP1, were deleted from the data set to obtain a clean factor loading. Table 1 shows the result of the factor analysis of this study.

Gerbing and Anderson (1988) claim that reliability proves the accuracy of measurement items. From the data shown in Table 2, it is clear that for all latent constructs, Cronbach's Alpha ranged from 0.700 to 0.814, which is within the recommended value as suggested by the extant literature (Nunnally, 1978).

Table 1 : The Result of Factor Analysis (Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring and Rotation Method: Promax)

Factors		F1	F2	F3
Economic Performance	ECOP2	0.711		
	ECOP3	0.603		
	ECOP4	0.747		
Environmental Performance	ENVP1		0.766	
	ENVP2		0.806	
	ENVP3		0.716	
Social Performance	SOCP2			0.698
	SOCP3			0.638
	SOCP4			0.724
Eigen Values		1.58	5.68	1.44

Note : ECOP: Economic Performance; ENVP: Environmental Performance; SOCP: Social Performance.

Table 2 : Reliability Measure – Cronbach's Alpha

Measuring Items		Cronbach's alpha	Type
Economic Performance (ECOP)		0.729	High Reliability
	ECOP2		
	ECOP3		
	ECOP4		
Environmental Performance (ENVP)		0.814	High Reliability
	ENVP1		
	ENVP2		
	ENVP3		
Social Performance (SOCP)		0.730	High Reliability
	SOCP2		
	SOCP3		
	SOCP4		

Validity is defined as the extent to which any measuring instrument measures what it is intended to measure (Bryman & Cramer, 2002; Carmines & Zeller, 1979). In this study, the instrument is reviewed by the academicians and RMG industry experts to ensure the content validity of the research instrument, item selection and refinement of the developed questionnaire. The Discriminant Validity test shows

how much variance in those indicators can explain variance in the construct (Said et al., 2011). Discriminant validity assessed by examining the correlations between the factors with the square root of the AVE for each factor as recommended by Fornell and Larcker (1981). The discriminant validity of each factor is established if the correlations among the factors are less than the square root of the AVE and the variance extracted for each factor exceeded 0.50 (Huang et al., 2016). As observed in Table 3, all correlations among the factors were less than the square root of the factor’s AVE. Table 3 also shows no correlations among factors greater than 0.85, as suggested by Kline (2005) to ensure discriminant validity.

Table 3 : Discriminant Validity of Measurement Model

	MN	SD	CR	AVE	ECOP	ENVP	SOCP
ECOP	3.94	0.78	0.731	0.516	0.718		
ENVP	4.15	0.67	0.814	0.594	0.517	0.771	
SOCP	4.14	0.67	0.728	0.504	0.375	0.395	0.709

Notes : MN: Mean; SD: Standard Deviation; CR: Composite Reliability; AVE: Average Variance Extracted; DV: Discriminant Validity; ENVP: Environmental Performance; ECOP: Economic Performance; SOCP: Social Performance.

4.1 Results of the Hypothesis Testing

Table 4 shows the results of the direct effects of impact of environmental and social performance on economic performance. The result indicates there exist a positive impact of both environmental and social performances on economic performance.

Table 4 : A Summary of the Multivariate Regression Analysis of both Environmental and Social Performance and its Impact on the Economic Performance

Hypothesis	Relationship		Standardised Regression weights	t-value	Sig-level (p- value)	Supported Hypothesis
	From	To				
H1 _a	ENVP	ECOP	0.519	5.936	<0.05	√
H1 _b	SCOP	ECOP	0.376	4.190	<0.05	√

Note: ECOP: Economic Performance; ENVP: Environmental Performance; SCOP: Social Performance; Results of structural equation modelling is significant where **p*<0.05; ***p*<0.01; ****p*<0.001.

Table 5 shows the summary of absolute, parsimony and relative-fit indices of the model used to evaluate direct relationships between constructs. For good model fitness, the values of χ^2 should be between 2.0 and 3.0, GFI, AGFI, CFI, TLI and NFI should be greater than 0.90, and the RMSEA should be between 0.06 to 0.08 (Schreiber et al., 2006). The fit indices were considered to be a good fit based on the complexity of the model and the context of social science research background.

Table 5 : Model-Fit Indices

χ^2	GFI	AGFI	CFI	TLI	NFI	RMSEA
1.650	0.98	0.96	0.99	0.99	0.96	0.031

5. DISCUSSION

Integration of sustainability practices in businesses has gained extensive attention in recent times owing to the escalating pressures from different stakeholder groups (Seuring & Muller, 2008; Diabat et al., 2014). Companies in the RMG sector are facing tremendous pressure to reduce the negative consequences of their business practices. To overcome this criticism, Bangladeshi RMG companies have started to adopt various sustainable business practices in their operations. These companies have become increasingly conscious of the competitive advantages associated with adopting SBPs in terms of various tangible and intangible returns over the last few years. Examples of tangible benefits include cleaner production, cost reduction, improved operational efficiency, improved health and safety practices, and increased market opportunities. On the other hand, examples of intangible benefits include improved company image and good working relationships with the IRs (International Retailers) and regulatory bodies.

The results of the hypothesis testing show that both improvements in environmental and social performances have a positive influence on a firm's economic performance in terms of increased profit margin and enhanced market share. Almost thirty years ago, Porter (1991) hypothesis speculated that regulatory strictness to improve environmental performance triggers innovation, allowing companies to achieve the double benefits of environmental protection and enhanced economic performance (Wong, 2013; Ambec et al., 2013). To date, several researchers work on testing this hypothesis and found that the implementation of environment-friendly business practices benefits companies and thus has a positive impact on enhancing their economic performance (Clemens, 2006; Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017). It is also evident from the current literature that companies can reduce their environmental impact by planning their environmentally-friendly business processes (Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017). This process helps them lower the costs of raw material through reuse and recycling, energy consumption and waste disposal, thus indirectly helping their economic bottom-line (Lampe et al., 1991; Porter & Van der Linde, 1995; Pullman et al., 2009). However, studies also reveal the negative impact of implementing environmentally friendly practises on the firm's economic performance (Ramanathan et al., 2010; Horváthová, 2012; Lucato et al., 2017). The results of a meta-analysis on 37 empirical works conducted by Horváthová (2012) exposed that the relationship between environmental performance and financial performance is indecisive. According to their study, half of the studies revealed that the consequence of implementing green practices has a positive impact which is in line with the findings of this study, while the remaining conclude with a negative or an insignificant impact (Horváthová, 2012). The main reason behind these mixed findings is that the firm has to dedicate a massive amount of money to plan and implement environment-

friendly business practices. The actual benefits become visible after successful implementation. The results of this study also are in line with the findings of those studies which found a positive effect of improved environmental performances on a firm's economic performance (Clemens, 2006; Hojnik & Ruzzier, 2017).

On the other hand, social performance was the most under-researched dimension in corporate sustainability performances. However, in recent time, equal attention to social issues along with the economic and environmental facets become necessary to deal with the hovering awareness on corporate social responsibility requirements (Çankaya et al., 2019). The socially responsible image of companies changes the customers' perception towards them and increases customers' willingness to buy specific brands, thereby helping profit maximization (Ganesan et al., 2009; Luo & Bhattacharya, 2006). The results of this study also agree with this assertion claimed by several researchers in this field (Ganesan et al., 2009; Luo & Bhattacharya, 2006; Çankaya et al., 2019). Furthermore, findings from several studies (Zhu & Sarkis, 2006; Dai et al., 2015; Govindan et al., 2015) who argued that ensuring social well-being such as employee welfare and safety was a crucial internal factor in improving a firm's economic performance (Eiadat et al., 2008; Yu & Choi, 2016).

As a low-price portfolio is the main attraction of the IRs when extending their supply chain to Bangladesh, IRs have been exerting continuous pressure on the RMG industry to maintain the low cost of the per-unit garment. In recent times, owing to the increase in energy, raw materials, utilities and transportation costs and a considerable rise in labor wages, it became challenging for RMG companies to maintain that low cost. IRs are also threatening to transfer their businesses to other countries if Bangladeshi RMG companies fail to ensure a low-price portfolio. In this scenario, those companies were trying to incorporate innovative SBPs to reduce cost reduction, which will help them in their CSP enhancement.

Due to some catastrophic factory-related tragedies, serious concerns were raised about unsustainable management practices in many RMG companies in Bangladesh. These types of catastrophic incidents project a very negative image to the partner companies and can cause severe damage to their brand image. In conjunction with these unfortunate incidents, ongoing employee protests for ensuring a fair wage, a safe working environment (i.e., building and fire safety, assurance of employee welfare, controlled usage of hazardous material) and labor rights campaigns were also pressurizing companies to implement different environmental and social practices. To overcome these problems, ensuring employee well-being is considered to be an important concern by those RMG companies wishing to survive in the international market. To ensure employee well-being, Bangladeshi RMG companies have started to adopt SBPs by improving health and safety practices such as assurance of fair wage, job security, pension plan, medical facilities and various insurance policies. These facilities improve employee satisfaction, retention, and productivity and improve overall sustainability performance, particularly in the social dimension. This study makes significant contributions to the sustainability performance management literature by investigating the relationship among the three important dimensions

of CSP, which provide a clear idea about the impact of environmental and social performances on economic performance in the developing country's context in general and RMG industry's perspective in particular.

The findings of this research study have several implications for the corporate managers of the RMG sector and industry associations and policymakers. Firstly, the survey results will provide corporate managers and policymakers with a comprehensive understanding of the relationship among all three dimensions of corporate sustainability performances (i.e., economic, environmental and social). The findings of this study also offer valuable insights to managerial decision-making by informing corporate managers and policymakers, the interlink among all three dimensions, and how the implementation of SBPs has a significant positive impact on a firm's economic performance.

6. CONCLUSION

The garment industry stands out as one of the most globalized industries in today's world. The RMG industry is a buyer-driven supply chain led by a coalition of retailers, contractors, subcontractors, merchandisers, buyers and suppliers. Bangladeshi RMG companies are mainly the first-tier suppliers of renowned international brands. Unsustainable business practices in any part of the supply chain affect all the affiliated partners. IRs are also exerting heavy pressure on these suppliers to comply with environmental and social requirements. Suppliers' cooperation is crucial in incorporating SBPs throughout the supply chain, as IRs are mostly dependent on those companies for manufacturing their products.

Furthermore, high expectations from government, NGOs, community and voluntary pressure groups (i.e., ILO and the Clean Clothes Campaign), and public media improve their corporate sustainability performance. Traditionally, these RMG organizations have been reluctant to incorporate sustainability concerns into their corporate policies and processes, owing to concerns that meeting environmental and social welfare requirements would increase costs, thereby jeopardizing economic sustainability (Kabir, 2017; Florida, 1996; Khor, 2011). In the past few years, RMG factories have started to make strides in terms of environmental and social business practices. However, those RMG companies are struggling to invest in the SBPs due to the continuous increases over the past few years in land, utilities, energy, and labor costs. It is becoming challenging for RMGs to survive in an intense market that involves fierce price competition for cheap labor alongside insistent demands for improved social and environmental performance. This study empirically illustrates that there is a positive impact of enhanced environmental and social performance on its economic performance.

6.1 Limitations and Future Work

Despite the significant empirical and practical contributions, which offer an excellent platform for understanding future research work, this study is subject to certain limitations. This study proposed a conceptual framework that was tested through a

cross-sectional questionnaire survey among the RMG companies of Bangladesh. The first limitation of the study is that as data were collected from one point in time, it was impossible to capture the changing dynamics over time, as in the longitudinal study. Future longitudinal studies can be conducted to understand better the constructs and relationships of the proposed conceptual framework over time. Furthermore, this study used a non-random sampling method called snowball sampling because the concept of sustainable business practices is considered an emerging phenomenon in the Bangladeshi RMG industry's context. Future studies may empirically test the proposed hypotheses using random sampling in the developed countries, where the awareness about sustainable business practices is much higher, to increase the generalizability of the results. Future research may identify and add new measurement items to operationalize performance variables in the model and empirically investigate its significance in the proposed conceptual framework. Each item was meticulously operationalized based on an extensive literature review to ensure high validity and reliability of the indicators. Hence, further in-depth analysis through qualitative research design can be performed to investigate the actual process of implementing SMCS within the organizations. Since the scope of the research is limited to the Bangladeshi RMG industry, which may undoubtedly restrict the generalizability of the findings to other industries like leather, automobile, manufacturing or energy. Further research could be conducted by replicating this study in other industries in different countries with larger sample size and other control variables. A comparative analysis can be performed from the results obtained from both developed and developing countries to provide much more comprehensive conclusions about the significance of different corporate sustainability performance indicators in each perspective. Future studies may include various supply chain partners to compare the differences in performances on multiple supply chain stages.

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Appendix 1

Table A1 : Operationalisation of Constructs

Constructs	Item	Measurement	Reference
Economic Performance (ECOP)	ECOP1	Increase in sales volume	Hojnik and Ruzzier 2017
	ECOP2	Increase in existing market share.	Chen et al., 2015
	ECOP3	Increase in profit margin.	Chan et al., 2016
	ECOP4	Increase in new market share.	Yu et al., 2017
Environmental Performance (ENVP)	ENVP1	Reduction in the consumption of hazardous and toxic materials.	Zhu et al., 2005; Paulraj, 2011
	ENVP2	Reduction in waste and consumption of energy and water.	Qu et al., 2015
	ENVP3	Implementation of an environmental management system (e.g., ISO 14001).	Yu et al., 2017
Social Performance (SOCP)	SOCP1	Attainment of social certifications (i.e. SA 8000, OHASIS)	Diabat et al. 2014
	SOCP2	Improvement in community development programs (e.g., health and education-related programs, donations to charitable organizations)	Chang et al., 2018
	SOCP3	Improvement in employee welfare programs (e.g., food and transportation allowances, maternity benefits, medical facilities).	Paulraj 2011
	SOCP4	Improvement in occupational health and safety practices (e.g., fire, building, chemical and electrical).	Chang et al., 2018